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Assessment of Students' Perception on STEM Education Implementation among Pre-service Mathematics Teachers' in Sokoto State University, Sokoto

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Abstract

The integration of Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) education is receiving attention globally where many countries are adopting it into their system of education. Therefore, the present study investigated the perceptions of Pre-service Mathematics teachers on STEM education. A correlational survey research design was used to collect data from 39 Pre-service mathematics teachers at Sokoto State University in Sokoto. A questionnaire titled pre-service mathematics teachers' perception on STEM with reliability index of 0.73 was used to collect data, about their views on STEM-related activities. Descriptive statistics were used to analyze data using mean and standard deviation. Whereas, partial correlation statistics was used to obtained the correlation among the variables. The results showed that there is moderate level of awareness, readiness, and experience, but a high level of confidence in implementing STEM education. Also, a higher correlation of confidence with another variable was found. The study recommends faculties and college of education should provide more awareness to pre-service teachers and give opportunities to the teachers to gain experience of STEM education in real-world contexts.

Keyword: STEM, Perception, Pre-service Mathematics Teachers, STEM Education

Introduction

In 21st century, Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) education is receiving more and more attention and it becoming a global phenomenon, with many countries incorporating it into their education systems. STEM is a term that had its origins and first coined the use of an acronym in the 1990s at the National Science Foundation (NSF) in the United States of America (USA). Hence, today the term is used

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as a common label for any event, program, policy and practice that involves one or numerous STEM fields (Galadima, 2024; Galadima, et.al 2019a). Accordingly, STEM is best understood as a discipline by removing the boundaries between the disciplines and taught as one discrete entity. The disciplines are combined into a single class focused on the connection between them and the idea for solving the real-world problem (Breiner *et al.*, 2012).

Also, STEM is considered as a unified amalgamation of concepts and content from multiple STEM disciplines in the curriculum through increasing focus on students' persistence in STEM (Kelley, & Knowles, 2016). Consequently, the connection between the STEM disciplines increases preparation and careers in developing the STEM-capable workforce that improves STEM literacy needs. The need for more engineers, technicians, scientists, and mathematicians (such as Software developers, Information security analyst, Architect, Actuarial Scientist, Cost estimators, Statistician, Web Developers, etc.). This necessitate for more innovative and creative workforce needed to compete and spar in a global marketplace (National Research Council. 2011). Taking together, this rationale supports the continually growing demand for the required STEM skills to meet the present and future global economic and social challenges. In view of this teacher institution need to develop and implement curricular for developing STEM skills to pre-service teachers.

Pre-service mathematics teachers are education students at the university levels who are receiving training to become the certified mathematics teachers for schools within a formal teacher education program (National Research Council, 2011). According to the study conducted by Koirala and Bowman (2003), indicated that pre-service teachers are much more likely to implement integrated teaching strategies within and during their teaching method course, particularly within their university methods courses. Due to limited researches in Sokoto State on pre-service mathematics teachers' preparation for STEM education, indicates the need for using PMTs who have yet to venture into the field to be at the forefront of the STEM movement. As the future leaders of the field, PMTs who are the novice to the field should be prepared for STEM education because they are the future leaders in the field who will play a vital role in steering the route of STEM education (Atkinson, & Mayo, 2010). This study provides meaningful learning opportunities for pre-service mathematics teachers to participate in STEM education to develop STEM competencies.

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STEM education competencies are prominent topic of discussion among educators since they involve in the processes of incorporating the four STEM disciplines. These competencies involve the awareness of the level of understanding and familiarity with STEM education concepts, principles, and practices (Abdioglu, et, al. 2021). While, experience as the extent of hands-on experience and engagement with STEM education activities, projects, and programs (Margot, & Kettler, 2019). Also, readiness is the level of preparedness and willingness to integrate STEM education into teaching practices (Sulaeman, et, al. 2022) and then confidence as the level of self-assurance in teaching STEM education subjects and integrating STEM education into teaching practices (Hoon, et, al. 2022; Stohlmann, et, al. 2012).

While, Pre-service teachers learn a variety of innovative and cutting-edge technologies and how to handle new pedagogical aspects, such as 21st century skills. This will enable the pre-service teachers to become familiar with 21st century STEM technologies. The question is whether the courses or trainings attended at universities to gain experience were sufficient to promote STEM practices in their future school career. To help PMTs implement STEM disciplines effectively and not only provide them with a positive understanding of STEM education but also improve their knowledge of STEM careers (Jiang, et, al. 2024). STEM awareness can be expressed as awareness of the relationships between STEM fields and the ability to draw logical conclusions. Subsequently, Abdioglu, et, al., (2021) defines STEM awareness as the promotion of higher-order thinking skills in individuals through STEM education, the ability to use STEM disciplines together, the understanding that a problem can be solved in different ways, and self-confidence and awareness that provide the ability to collaborate and build effective communication. Instead, STEM awareness is considered a prerequisite for interaction, self-efficacy and development (Abdioglu, et, al., 2021). Consequently, studies in the literature on STEM awareness show how important comprehensive STEM awareness of the individual is in addition to STEM education.

On the other hand, it is learned that experience is not acquired by learning; rather, it is evoked through collaboration to improve as the learner reflect and make judgement on their practices (Hoon, et, al., 2022). For this reason, experiences can be used as a guide for future STEM practices (Şenyiğit, & Bakırcı, 2025). In this respect, pre-service teachers found the experience they gained from other activities related to STEM were lesser (Dost, 2024). The year of experience confirm that novice teachers have a less positive view of STEM education than experienced teachers. In contrast, Srikoom, et,

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al., (2017); Margot, and Kettler, (2019), explain that teachers' year of experience appears to be inconsistent with teachers' perceptions of STEM education and that teachers' engagement in STEM education may mediate this inconsistent relationship. Likewise, Theo, et, al., (2024) added that as teachers gain more experience, their readiness to implement STEM subjects also increases, but only if they place a high value on STEM education.

In contrast, increasing number of experiences does not influence teachers' readiness to teach STEM subjects. Also, Margot and Kettler (2019) confirmed that pre-service teachers who valued STEM education not only increases their level of readiness to teach STEM, but also their desire to teaching STEM education. However, pre-service teacher who did not value STEM education did not demonstrate higher level of readiness with more years of experience (Ramli, et, al., 2017). Perhaps valuing this type of pedagogy will lead to an improvement in pre-service teachers' readiness, and this variable should be considered more frequently. With the spread of STEM education, teacher readiness has become an essential component, especially in how they train teachers (Margot & Kettler, 2019) and build their readiness in STEM education (El-Deghaidy, et, al., 2017; Sulaeman, et, al., 2022). Other researchers argue that readiness refers to the extent to which teachers demonstrate willingness and confidence to take responsibility for their own teaching (Hung, 2016). Stohnlmann et al. (2012) found that teachers' passion for STEM education influenced their confidence and comfort in implementing the curriculum. The PMTs confidence is generally defined as a belief in one's own abilities or the degree of confidence a person has in his or her abilities or, in the case of STEM, a person's ability to learn well and perform well in STEM education (Şenyiğit, & Bakırcı, 2025). Confidence has further been defined in this study as the teacher's belief in assessing to establish their perceived capabilities in STEM education. In view of the present study deem it imperative to investigate the per-service mathematics teachers' perception after engagement with STEM activities in their methodology course.

Statement of the Research Problem

STEM education is an important area that help towards actualizing the 21st century skills and continue to receive more concern globally. Despite the importance of STEM skills toward national development, the reality in Nigeria, STEM education are taught as single subject, and that the perception of pre-service mathematics teachers on STEM education is not well understood due to lack of a clear curriculum that combines

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the science, technology, engineering and mathematics (Galadima., 2023; 2024). Still, each of the STEM disciplines is considered as a separate and distinct field of study (Galadima, et.al, 2019b). In this regard, the use of STEM approach would provide opportunities with a more relevant, more meaningful learning experience and less fragmented knowledge (Furner & Kumar, 2007). In relation to solving real-world problems, single disciplines prevent the PMTs from building the needed competencies and connection between and among the four fields of STEM (Kalolo, 2016). Subsequently, real-world problems are not fragmented and isolated in single disciplines as they are taught in the school's curriculum of Sokoto State Nigeria.

Thus, to solve the problems of teaching in a single discipline, people need skills that make sense of learning content cut across the disciplines. literature affirmed that the learners need prepare for the global demands of the 21st-century through STEM education (Thibaut et al., 2018). The 21st-century demand needs for workers to have the knowledge of mathematics skills and science, creativity, expertise in communication and information technology, and the capability to solve complex real-world problems (Jayarajah, et, al., 2014). The STEM practices help to determine whether Sokoto State Nigeria will be able to solve tremendous challenges in teaching individual STEM disciplines without connection between and among the disciplines per se. In bridging this gap, this study investigated the perception of pre-service mathematics teachers on STEM education at Sokoto State University, Sokoto, with a focus on awareness, experience, readiness, and confidence.

Objectives of the study

The following objectives were developed to guide the study

1. Assess the mean response of level of awareness of STEM education implementation among pre-service Mathematics teachers in Sokoto State University.
2. Assess the mean response of level of experience of STEM education implementation among pre-service Mathematics teachers in Sokoto State University.
3. Assess the mean response of level of readiness of STEM education implementation among pre-service Mathematics teachers in Sokoto State University.
4. Assess the mean response of level of confidence of STEM education implementation among pre-service Mathematics teachers in Sokoto State University.
5. Find out the Preservice Mathematics Teachers' level of confidence and its relationship with awareness, experience, and readiness on STEM education.

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Research Questions

This study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What is the mean response of level of awareness of STEM education implementation among pre-service Mathematics teachers in Sokoto State University?
2. What is the mean response of level of experience of STEM education implementation among pre-service Mathematics teachers in Sokoto State University?
3. What is the mean response of level of readiness of STEM education implementation among pre-service Mathematics teachers in Sokoto State University?
4. What is the mean response of level of confidence of STEM education implementation among pre-service Mathematics teachers in Sokoto State University?
5. Are there any relationships between the Preservice Mathematics Teachers' perceptions of confidence and its relationship with awareness, experience, and readiness to teach STEM education?

Hypotheses

1. There is no any relationships between the Preservice Mathematics Teachers' level of confidence and its relationship with awareness, experience, and readiness on STEM education.

Methodology

A correlational survey research design design was adopted in this study. The design will help to explain the relationship between both independent and dependent variables. Participants in the present research were selected from pre-service mathematics teachers at Sokoto State University, Sokoto, Nigeria. A total of 39 students were involved, using intact class. Thus to ensure the ethical standard all the participants (Mathematics pre-service teachers) were told that their names would be kept confidential and anonymous. As such all the participating pre-service teachers agreed to participate. However, to assess the pre-service mathematics teachers' perception a 20 items questionnaire based on STEM competencies was developed. After expert validation, modifications were made, pilot tested and reliability index was obtained with a Cronbach's 0.73, the acceptable Cronbach's alpha value is ranging

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between 0.7 to 0.95. The results obtained were analysed using descriptive statistics to describe the perception of the respondents about the implementation of STEM education and partial correlation were used to analyze the relationship among the variables.

Presentation of Results

In this section the result of five research questions and one hypothesis were answer as explained in methodology using tables as follows.

Research Question 1

What is the mean response of level of awareness of STEM education implementation among pre-service Mathematics teachers in Sokoto State University?

Table 1: PMTs Perception on the Awareness to Teach STEM Education

S/N	Questionnaire Items	N	Mean (M)	Std. Deviation (SD)
1	I am familiar with the concept of STEM education	39	3.87	0.83
2	I have a clear understanding of how to integrate mathematics with other STEM subjects.	39	3.23	0.91
3	I am aware of the various teaching strategies used in STEM education.	39	4.03	0.67
4	I am familiar with the use of technology in STEM education.	39	3.46	0.85
5	I have knowledge of the resources and materials available in teaching STEM education.	39	3.92	0.76

Table1 shows the results of 39 PMTs level of awareness on STEM education. The mean and the SD of 3.87(0.83); 4.03(0.67) and 3.92(0.76) indicated that the respondents tend to agree that they are familiar with the concept, aware with the various teaching strategies and have the knowledge of resources and materials in teaching STEM education. Whereas, the mean and the SD of 3.23(0.91) and 3.46(0.85) indicated that the respondents tend to be neutral about having a clear understanding of how to integrate mathematics with other STEM disciplines and their familiarity with the use of technology in STEM education.

Research Question 2

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What is the mean response of level of experience of STEM education implementation among pre-service Mathematics teachers in Sokoto State University?

Table 2: PMTs Perception on the Experience to Teach STEM Education

S/N	Questionnaire Items	N	Mean (M)	Std. Deviation (SD)
1	I have experience in teaching mathematics in a way that integrates with other STEM subjects.	39	2.85	0.92
2	I have used technology to support student learning in mathematics and other STEM subjects.	39	3.38	0.81
3	I have experience in designing and implementing STEM-based projects in the classroom.	39	2.59	0.95
4	I have experience in assessing student learning in STEM subjects using a variety of methods.	39	3.08	0.88
5	I have experience in collaborating with other teachers to develop and implement STEM education programs.	39	2.82	0.93

Table 2 shows the results of 39 PMTs level of experience on STEM education. The mean and the SD of 2.85(0.92); 2.59(0.95), and 2.82(0.93) indicated that the respondents tend to disagree that they have experience in teaching mathematics in a way that integrates with other STEM subjects; designing and implementing STEM-based projects in the classroom; and that they have experience in collaborating with other teachers in developing STEM education programs. Whereas, the mean and the SD of 3.38(0.81) and 3.08(0.88) indicated that the respondents tend to be neutral about using technology to support student learning in mathematics and other STEM subjects and about having experience in assessing student learning in STEM subjects using a variety of methods.

Research Question 3

What is the mean response of level of experience of STEM education implementation among pre-service Mathematics teachers in Sokoto State University?

Table 3: PMTs Perception for their Readiness to Teach STEM Education

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S/N	Questionnaire Items	N	Mean (M)	Std. Deviation (SD)
1	I am ready and prepared to teach mathematics in a way that integrates with other STEM subjects.	39	3.59	0.81
2	I have the necessary skills to use technology to support student learning in STEM subjects.	39	3.85	0.74
3	I am ready in my ability to design and implement STEM-based projects in the classroom.	39	3.31	0.89
4	I am prepared to assess student learning in STEM subjects using a variety of methods.	39	3.54	0.83
5	I am ready in my ability to teach STEM subjects in a way that promotes critical thinking and problem-solving.	39	3.67	0.79

Table 3 shows the results of 39 PMTs level of readiness on STEM education. The mean and the SD of 3.59(0.81); 3.85(0.74); 3.54(0.83) and 3.67(0.79) indicated that the respondents tend to agree that they are ready and well prepared to teach mathematics in a way that integrates with other STEM subjects; having necessary skills to use technology to support student learning in STEM subjects; prepared to assess student learning in STEM subjects using a variety of methods; and their confidence in their ability to teach STEM subjects in a way that promotes critical thinking and problem-solving. Whereas, the only mean with SD of 3.31(0.89) indicated the respondents tend to be neutral about their readiness in designing and implementing STEM-based projects in the classroom.

Research Question 4

What is the mean response of level of confidence of STEM education implementation among pre-service Mathematics teachers in Sokoto State University?

Table 4: PMTs Perception of their Confidence to Teach STEM Education

S/N	Questionnaire Items	N	Mean (M)	Std. Deviation (SD)
1	I am confident in my ability to teach mathematics in a way that integrates with other STEM subjects.	39	3.92	0.71
2	I am confident in my ability to use technology to support student learning in STEM subjects.	39	4.03	0.65
3	I am confident in my ability to design and implement STEM-based projects in the classroom.	39	3.62	0.81

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4	I am confident in my ability to assess student learning in STEM subjects using a variety of methods.	39	3.85	0.73
5	I am confident in my ability to teach STEM subjects in a way that promotes critical thinking and problem-solving.	39	3.97	0.69

Table 4 shows the results of 39 PMTs level of confidence on STEM education. The mean of all the items indicated that the respondents agreed that they are confident in their ability to teach STEM education. Whereas, the SD of all the items indicated relatively low level of variability in the participants responses.

Research Question 5

Are there any relationships between the Preservice Mathematics Teachers' perceptions of confidence and its relationship with awareness, experience, and readiness to teach STEM education?

Table 5 : Mean and Standard Deviation of the Perceived Levels of STEM Education

S/N	Perceived Levels	N	Mean (M)	Std. Deviation (SD)
1	Awareness	39	3.70	0.81
2	Experience	39	2.94	0.89
3	Readiness	39	3.59	0.81
4	Confidence	39	3.88	0.72

Table 5 presented the results of 39 PMTs regarding their level of awareness, experience, readiness, and confidence on STEM education. The PMTs awareness was rated with the mean of 3.70 and (SD=0.81). Nonetheless, they rated comparatively higher than their experience and readiness with mean of 2.94 and 3.59 (SD=0.89 and 0.81). With these, the PMTs were more confident with the mean of 3.88 (SD=0.72) in their ability to teach STEM subjects.

Hypothesis 1

There is no any relationship between the Preservice Mathematics Teachers' level of confidence and its relationship with awareness, experience, and readiness on STEM education.

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Table 6. Partial Correlation of Confidence with Awareness, Experience, and Readiness

Confidence		
Awareness	Partial Correlation	0.53**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.01
	N	39
Experience	Partial Correlation	0.41**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.01
	N	39
Readiness	Partial Correlation	0.68**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.01
	N	39

Table 6 highlights the results of partial correlation of confidence and its relationship with awareness, experience, and readiness. The results indicated that the confidence has significant positive correlation with awareness ($r = 0.53$, $p < 0.01$), experience ($r = 0.41$, $p < 0.01$), and readiness ($r = 0.68$, $p < 0.01$). The results show all the factors are essential in ensuring achievement of knowledge in STEM education. Interestingly, the results indicated the highest correlation between readiness and confidence balanced in STEM education.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study revealed that pre-service mathematics teachers recognize the value of STEM education and its relevance to the modern world. Their awareness and intention towards STEM education promote higher-order thinking skills and influenced collaboration to build effective communication (Abdioglu, Çevik, & Kosar, 2021). Thus, Jiang, Zhang, and Zhang, (2024) stated that awareness of STEM disciplines effectively and not only provide them with a positive understanding of STEM education but also improve their knowledge of STEM careers. On the connection between awareness and confidence it can be seen in table 6 the PMTs who are more aware of the importance of teaching STEM education tend to be more confident in their ability to teach it, independent of their experience and readiness.

However, the results also show that pre-service mathematics teachers lack experience in teaching STEM education. This is not surprising, given that many teacher education programs may not provide adequate opportunities for pre-service teachers to gain practical experience in teaching STEM subjects (Baptista, Conceição, & Filipe, 2025).

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The experience is exceptionally essential since the result also shows that there is a relationship between experience and confidence (Şenyiğit, & Bakırcı, 2025). Nevertheless, the pre-service teachers found the experience they gained from other activities related to STEM were lesser (Dost, 2024). PMTs year of experience confirm that novice teachers have a less positive view of STEM education than experienced teachers (Galadima, Ismail, & Ismail, 2019). Even though PMTs were less experienced, they responded positively to the level of confidence. (Şenyiğit, & Bakırcı, 2025).

In terms of readiness, the findings revealed that pre-service mathematics teachers are moderately ready to teach STEM education. This indicates that while they may have some knowledge and skills, they may still require additional support and training to feel fully prepared (Ramli, Ibrahim, Surif, Bunyamin, Jamaluddin, & Abdullah, 2017). The analysis focused on understanding teachers' opinions on their readiness to teach STEM education. In this study, results showed that moderate respondents were ready to teach STEM and showing interested in STEM. With the spread of STEM education, teacher readiness has become an essential component, especially in how they train teachers (Margot & Kettler, 2019; Sulaeman, Efwinda, & Putra, 2022) and build their readiness in STEM education (El-Deghaidy, Mansour, Alzaghibi, & Alhammad, 2017).

Finally, the results show that pre-service mathematics teachers are moderately confident in their ability to teach STEM education. This suggests that while they may have some doubts and uncertainties, they are generally positive about their ability to teach STEM subjects (Hoon, Aris, Ibrahim, & Isa, 2022). The confidence level provides a direction on the PMTs plans and ability to conduct lessons with STEM elements in schools or other institutions. According to the findings of this study, students require more experience to gain confidence in guiding the next generation through school activities. All parties benefit from the activities, which support and respond to the growing STEM activities (Solanki et al., 2019).

Conclusion

From the finding of this study, we can conclude that teachers' readiness in implementing STEM education is still at a low level. The present study indicated that pre-service mathematics teachers' have high level of confidence in in their ability to STEM education was highly associated to experience, even though the level of experience was rated lower when compared to readiness and effort. On the other hand, there are positive correlation between the confidence and awareness, experience, and readiness to teach STEM education. Also, the study showed that awareness,

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experience, and readiness are interconnected and influenced one another, which in turn affect confidence. Therefore, it is essential to address these variables simultaneously to enhance pre-service teachers' confidence on STEM education.

Recommendations

The following recommendations could be useful based on the findings of this study:

1. Regular workshops and seminars should be organized to enhance pre-service mathematics teachers' awareness of STEM education, such as its importance, and its implementation strategies.
2. Pre-service mathematics teachers should be provided with opportunities to participate in hands-on STEM education activities, such as internships, volunteer teaching, to gain practical experience.
3. A readiness program should be developed and implemented to prepare pre-service mathematics teachers for STEM education implementation, focusing on developing their skills, knowledge, and attitudes.
4. Mentorship programs should be established to pair pre-service mathematics teachers with experienced teachers or mentors who can provide guidance, support, and feedback to boost their confidence in implementing STEM education.
5. Intervention should be developed to enhance pre-service mathematics teachers' level of confidence and awareness, experience, and readiness on STEM education. This could include the training programs and mentorship to address areas of concern in implementing STEM education.

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